

IRMA: Individual physiological reaction patterns during surgical procedures using the example of laparoscopic surgery

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Abstract: Fusing data from multiple medical disciplines in the operating room (OR) is essential for creating intelligent context-aware systems that improve interdisciplinary awareness and patient outcomes. Effective data fusion required two key aspects to be fulfilled. The first aspect is the synchronised data acquisition from medical devices. The second aspect is analysing the relationships between data coming from different devices. This project explores the correlation between intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) and lung mechanics of the patient during laparoscopic procedures. Statistical analysis revealed high correlation between IAP and both dynamic lung compliance and peak airway pressure (PIP) with mean Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.887 and 0.934, respectively. The results of this project support the development of the future systems in OR that provide a comprehensive information about the surgical and patient status and improve collaboration between medical teams.

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I. Introduction

Operating rooms (ORs) have transformed significantly with the advent of modern medical technologies. While these innovations assist medical teams during procedures, each device typically provides information limited to its specific functions or patient parameters. Processing and integrating all of this data is challenging, as it often overwhelms medical operators. Consequently, medical teams tend to focus on the information most relevant to their specific roles and tasks, which can lead to fragmented awareness of the overall situation. Therefore, intelligent systems that analyse all available data are becoming indispensable in the OR of the future [1–4]. These systems have diverse potential applications. Intraoperatively, they can enhance comprehensive awareness of both surgical and patient status, facilitating better collaboration between medical teams and reducing the risk of conflicts amongst them. Furthermore, intelligent systems can optimize the surgical workflow by assisting decision-making, preventing avoidable complications through promptly alerting the surgical or anaesthesiological team, and predicting remaining procedural time to improve OR resource management efficiency [5–7]. Postoperatively, they enable automatic generation of reports. To facilitate the documentation and post-operative analysis [8].

This project takes a step towards developing such intelligent systems by fusing and analysing data from multiple medical disciplines, specifically surgery and anaesthesiology. This project aims to study the correlation between surgical data provided by surgical devices and physiological measurement of the patient. In particular, the relationship between intra-abdominal pressure induced by

insufflating the abdominal cavity of the patient and the patient's lung mechanics was assessed and analysed.

II. Material and methods

II.I. Data recording

A data recording framework was established in an integrated operating room (OR1 Fusion) to collect the data from surgical devices and the physiological data of the patient [9]. The integrated operating room allows data collection from interconnected devices through a certain communication bus. These devices provided by KARL STORZ SE & Co.KG (Tuttlingen, Germany) are insufflation unit, surgical motor system, endoscopic light source, irrigation pump and laparoscopic camera. Additionally, an electrosurgical unit (Erbe GmbH) was connected to Storz communication bus using an interface device enabling data collection of this device. Patient physiological parameters were recorded by capturing data from the anaesthesia machine and patient monitor.

The required software for acquiring the data from surgical devices, patient monitor and anaesthesia machine were developed. Data recording was carried out using a computer installed in a technical room in the surgical department.

II.II. Data types

Various data types were collected from anaesthesia machine, patient monitor and surgical devices during the laparoscopic procedures. The recorded data includes settings of anaesthesia machine and ventilation such as ventilation mode and positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP). Additionally, real-time values for ventilation

parameters such as the tidal volume (V_T), and real-time data streams for airway pressure, flow, volume, CO_2 , O_2 , N_2O , and anaesthetic agent levels were acquired. Data obtained from the patient monitor includes heart rate, body temperature, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, and perfusion indicator. ECG and SpO_2 signals were also recorded.

The laparoscopic video was captured at a rate of 25 frames per second. Cutting and coagulation signals were acquired from the electrosurgical unit. Furthermore, the intra-abdominal pressure, flow and volume provided by the insufflation unit were obtained. Additionally, the irrigation flow, pressure and volume were acquired. The status and intensity of the endoscopic light source were captured.

The collected data allow monitoring and analysis of patient status and procedural parameters throughout the laparoscopic procedure.

III. Results and discussion

In this project, a data recording system was implemented to collect data from medical devices during laparoscopic procedures. The system allowed the collection of combined surgical and patient-specific data generating a unique multi-prospective dataset. Data analysis was conducted to investigate the correlation between surgical actions and changes in patient respiratory mechanics [10–13].

Statistical analysis was conducted on data from patients undergoing different ventilation settings specifically pressure-controlled ventilation (PCV) and volume-controlled ventilation (VCV) [10]. The correlation between the IAP and dynamic lung compliance (C_{dyn}), peak airway pressure (PIP) and tidal volume were estimated using Pearson's correlation coefficient in a linear regression analysis. Moreover, a multivariate linear regression (MLR) analysis was conducted considering changes of ventilation setting such as respiration rate, inspiration/expiration ratio, PEEP, the pre-set inspiration pressure for PCV and target tidal volume for VCV.

Results demonstrate strong correlation between IAP and lung mechanics. In MLR analysis, the mean Pearson's correlation coefficient between IAP and dynamic lung compliance across the subjects is 0.887. High correlations were observed in both PCV and VCV ventilation modes. Table 1 presents correlation results for MLR analysis over all patients, PCV patients and VCV patients.

Table 1: Pearson's correlation coefficient in the MLR analysis between IAP and both C_{dyn} and PIP.

	C_{dyn}	PIP	V_T
PCV patients	0.908	0.954	0.735
VCV Patients	0.910	0.928	-
All	0.887	0.934	-

The increase of IAP affects the ventilating parameters of the patient. For patients on PCV, increasing IAP results in a drop in the tidal volume as the ventilator keep delivering the target pressure. Similarly, reductions in IAP also influence tidal volume. In contrast, for volume-controlled

ventilation (VCV) patients, anaesthesia machine maintains the target tidal volume, but changes in IAP still affect ventilation parameters such as peak airway pressure.

IV. Conclusions

This project demonstrates the impact of intra-abdominal pressure on lung mechanics during laparoscopic procedures. Strong correlations identified in the statistical analysis highlight the potential of integrating data from anaesthesiology and surgery to provide a comprehensive view of patient's intraoperative status and improve situational awareness for the surgical team.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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